

STUDYING PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS FOR FORMING BASIC QUALITIES IN YOUTH BASED ON NATIONAL VALUES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11277349>

Annotation: In this topic, you can familiarize yourself with empirical data on such issues as the psychological characteristics of raising young people in modern families with the help of national values, young people's ideas about national and family values, attitudes towards raising children in the family, the level of knowledge of parents about methods of raising children.

Keywords: modern family, national value, family value, national education, virtue, characteristics.

Goal of the work. Finding ways to form a new systematic approach to modern youth education based on national values, studying its psychological mechanisms in guaranteeing the formation of basic qualities in young people, in this matter - family, preschool education, general secondary, specialized secondary vocational, to fully reveal the social and pedagogical potential of higher educational institutions, microdistricts and raise scientific and methodological unity between them to a new level.

Materials and methods. The questionnaire was taken from 50 1st level students of the department "National Idea, Spiritual Foundations and Legal Education" of the Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of Pedagogy and Social Sciences.

1. ValueIt was found that when asked what you mean by National customs, traditions and national holidays - 29 (58%) people, respect for adults, respect for children, care, mutual trust - 3 (6%) people, national cultural values, moral values - 7 (14%) people, peace, justice, mutual respect, unity, customs, traditions, cultural and spiritual wealth important for humanity - 11 (22%) students were able to answer.

2. The family answered the question of what could be included in values as follows. Holidays are celebrated in the family circle, traditions by 3 (6%) people, respect for parents, affection for children, the dominant position of the father in the family - 27 (54%) people, food etiquette, adults serve food first, eating food with the blessing of adults after death - 9 (18%) people, all moral standards are inherited from parents, respect for old age, mutual trust, duty and

responsibility, education - 8 (16%) people, equality of husband and wife, peace and harmony - 3 were able to answer (6%) students.

3. What do you mean by national value?: Nowruz, Independence Day, Ramadan and Kurban-Id - 18 (36%) people, national traditions inherited from fathers and grandfathers, traditional rituals - 20 (40%) people, harmony, hospitality, tolerance - 10 (20%) students, national clothes and national food, historical and cultural monuments - 2 (4%) students were able to answer.

Summary. In conclusion, it should be said that the formation of the virtue of respect for national and family values in the family, as well as raising children, are the efforts of parents in the happiness of the family and the development of the individual. Children into mature people. Instilling values in the family plays an important role in the future development of the child. So, in the family, the child sees the image of society; in the family, the character, worldview and moral character of the future citizen are formed and mature accordingly.

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